

Developing a DDI-Driven Data Visualization Application in Dataverse

By: Kevin Worthington,
Applications Programmer/Analyst - Data
& GIS Services, OCUL Scholars Portal

Date: April 7th, 2017

Scholars Portal and OCUL

- Digital library infrastructure for the 21 University Libraries in Ontario, Canada
- Provide Data and GIS services to the libraries and researchers across the province
- <odesi> (<http://odesi.ca>),
- Scholars GeoPortal (<http://geo.scholarsportal.info>),
- Dataverse (<http://dataverse.scholarsportal.info>)

Find data:

video games Anywhere +

Date: Earliest Present

<odesi> contains over 3,535 datasets for the social sciences, with more than 13,000 additional dataset descriptions available for searching.

[Learn more](#)

Collections:

All of <odesi>

- Statistics Canada (Microdata) ⓘ
- Statistics Canada (Aggregate data) ⓘ
- Public Opinion Polls ⓘ
- Other Data ⓘ

Additional Collections:

- Statistics Canada (Master File) ⓘ
- CORA ⓘ
- ICPSR ⓘ
- Canadian Dataverses ⓘ

[Search](#)

Results Showing 1 to 10 of about 145

Sort By: Relevance Date

[Need help?](#)

General Social Survey, Cycle 12, 1998 [Canada]: Time Use, Main File

The two primary objectives of Cycle 12 are: to gather data on social trends in order to monitor temporal changes in the living conditions and well-being of Canadians; and to provide immediate information on specific social policy issues of current ... [show more](#)

Matching Variables 2

[Explore & Download](#) ↗

Survey of Household Spending, 2008 [Canada]

The 2008 Survey of Household Spending was carried out in private households in Canada's 10 provinces and three territories. Detailed information was collected about expenditures for consumer goods and services, changes in assets, mortgages and ... [show more](#)

Matching Variables 4

[Explore & Download](#) ↗

Limit your search:

Keyword

education 64

income 52

value 34

trade 33

country codes 32

[+ More](#)

Scholars GeoPortal

Scholars GeoPortal

Search

Map (1)

Download

Login

Data Place or address

Anywhere

Search

Downloadable content only

[Back To Downloads](#)

Cartographic Boundary Files (CBF), 1996 Census - Census Divisions

Add - 1/13

Producer: Statistics Canada
Date published: 1997-04-01 (publication)
Type of data layer: Vector

Permalink http://geo.scholarsportal.info/#r/details/_uri@=3577293255

Coordinate system: 4269 - "NAD83"

Abstract:

The Census Divisions (CD) Boundary File contains the boundaries of all 288 census divisions in Canada for the 1996 Census.

A Census Division is the general term for provincially legislated areas (such as counties, municipalities, and regional districts), or their equivalents. Census divisions are intermediate geographic areas between the province or territorial level and the municipality (census subdivisions).

The original data files are from the Data Liberation Initiative (DLI), a Statistics Canada program that provides data to academic institutions in Canada. The original files have been converted from the Arcinfo Interchange E00 file format (.e00) or the MapInfo TAB file format (.tab) into a shapefile format (.shp), as part of a data migration project to enhance the spatial use of the data. The original data files, and other supporting files and documentation, are available as additional downloads from Scholars GeoPortal.

Save Share Print Export Data Table Base Maps Contact Français

If you are off-campus, please login

Research data

- Researchers collect a ton of research data! More awareness of the need to share it with others
- Libraries are providing services to support researcher with RDM
- Dataverse was adopted as a library hosted institutional data repository in Ontario in 2011

Dataverse @SP

Scholars Portal **Dataverse**

Search all dataverses...

Search

About

Guides ▾

Support

Sign Up

Log In

Fr (Beta)

SCHOLARS PORTAL RESEARCH DATA PLATFORM

Publish and track your data, discover and reuse others' data!

Create My Dataverse

or Explore

Algoma
UNIVERSITY

Algoma University Dataverse

Brock
University

Brock University Dataverse

 Carleton
UNIVERSITY

Carleton University Dataverse

 Lakehead
UNIVERSITY

Lakehead University Dataverse

What is ^{The} **Dataverse** _{Project}

- Open source research data repository
- For organizing, sharing/promoting, research replicability and archiving data
- Developed by Harvard's Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS)
- Predecessor projects
 - Virtual Data Center (VDC) (1999-2006) for collaboration with MIT
 - Automatic transfer of cataloging information using FTP (1987-1999)

Dataverse Features

- Supports uploading of any file format
 - .zip, .xls, spss, sas, stata, pdf, doc, etc.
 - Version Control
 - Tab file generation
- Allows Administration
 - Data management
 - Organize, Create, Update, Delete, Feature
 - Roles and Permissions at the file-level
 - Terms of Use
 - Theming
 - Metadata curation
- Persistent ID support
- API's
- Sharable widgets

Scholars Portal Dataverse Usage

- Deployed Ver. 3.6 at SP in 2011
- Self-deposit model (anyone can signup and deposit data)
- Currently have
 - 176 Dataverses
 - 801 Datasets
 - 15,562 Files
- 13 OCUL libraries using it
- Curating multidisciplinary data
- All to satisfy the growing need to deposit and share research data easily with others

New Features from Upgrade

- DataCite Canada Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)
 - DOI minting for new data deposits
- Extended metadata support
 - Health & Life Sciences, Geosciences, Social Sciences, Astronomy, Journals
 - Harvesting and Export support with OAI-PMH
- Nested Dataverses ➡
- Shibboleth support (SSO)
- Revised Data Exploring 😞

Dataverse Before

Scholars Portal **Dataverse**
A Service of the Ontario Council of University Libraries

SP Dataverse Network

🔍 ⓘ 🗨️ [Create Account](#) [University of Toronto IP Group](#) [Log In](#)

[Advanced Search](#) [Tips](#)

The Scholars Portal Dataverse network is a repository for research data collected by individuals and organizations associated with Ontario universities. The Dataverse platform makes it easy for researchers to deposit data, create appropriate metadata, and version documents as you work. Access to data and supporting documentation can be controlled down to the file level, and researchers can choose to make content available publicly, only to select individuals, or to keep it completely locked. All data is hosted on Canadian servers, in a secure environment that conforms to industry best practices for maintaining data integrity and longevity.

For more information on Scholars Portal Dataverse, visit [Dataverse at Scholars Portal](#).

Dataverses

78 Dataverses

i A **Dataverse** is a container for research data studies, customized and managed by its owner.

RECENTLY RELEASED DATAVERSES

Biofield Energy Treatment Mahendra Trivedi	Aug 8, 2016
aidenstoker	Jul 27, 2016
Open Driver Vehicle Licensing - Shared Services Centre (SSC CA) DVLA	Jun 27, 2016
iSquare	May 30, 2016
Lynn Rempel	May 13, 2016

[View More >](#)

Studies

650 Studies, **6,931** Files, **21,109** Downloads

i A **study** is a container for a research data set. It includes cataloging information, data files and complementary files.

RECENTLY RELEASED STUDIES

Impact of Biofield Treatment on Growth and Yield of Lettuce and Tomato by Mahendra Kumar Trivedi	Sep 26, 2016
Biofield and Fungicide Seed Treatment Influences on Soybean Productivity, Seed Quality and Weed Community	Sep 26, 2016
Influence of Biofield Energy Treatment on Isotopic Abundance Ratio in Aniline Derivatives by Mahendra Kumar Trivedi	Sep 26, 2016
Evaluation of Isotopic Abundance Ratio in Naphthalene Derivatives After Biofield Energy Treatment Using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry by Mahendra Kumar Trivedi	Sep 26, 2016
Characterization of Physicochemical and Thermal Properties of Biofield Treated Ethyl Cellulose and Methyl Cellulose by Mahendra Kumar Trivedi	Sep 26, 2016

[View More >](#)

MOST DOWNLOADED STUDIES

Forum Research Political Poll – Federal Issues 2013	1896
Fair Access to Government Manuals Project by Citizenship and Immigration Canada	1822

Silver Data Dataverse

MYSPEACE GENRES

[< View Previous Study Listing](#)

hdl:10864/11402UNF:5:2W7x1+2m2IZPD68+wjb2XQ==

Version: 1 – Released: Tue Jan 19 14:43:12 EST 2016

[Cataloging Information](#)

DATA & ANALYSIS

[Comments \(0\)](#)

[Versions](#)

i Use the check boxes next to the file name to download multiple files. Data files will be downloaded in their default format. You can also download all the files in a category by checking the box next to the category name. You will be prompted to save a single archive file. Study files that have restricted access will not be downloaded.

Select all files

Total Number of Files: **2** Total Downloads: **11**

<input type="checkbox"/> Data File		
<input type="checkbox"/> MySpaceGenres.tab	Tab Delimited - 138 MB - 9 downloads + analyses MD5 Checksum: 01c6aaf5155ad760a40b962fd5566ac9 TABULAR DATA 2883141 Cases 5 Variables	<input type="button" value="Download as..."/> <input type="button" value="Access Analysis + Subsetting"/> <input type="button" value="View Data Citation [+]"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Documentation		
<input type="checkbox"/> MySpace Codebook.docx	application/octet-stream - 68 KB - 2 downloads MD5 Checksum: 2cba90b75aad4e8bfa9fdcccef7a7eba	<input type="button" value="Download"/> Codebook for MySpaceGenres.tab

Silver Data Dataverse

MYSFACE GENRES

[< Back to Study](#)

hdl:10864/11402UNF:5:2W7x1+2m2IZPD68+wjb2XQ==

Version: 1 – Released: Tue Jan 19 14:43:12 EST 2016

Data File: MySpaceGenres.tab

DOWNLOAD SUBSET

[Recode & Case-Subset](#)

[Descriptive Statistics](#)

[Advanced Statistical Analysis](#)

Selected Variables

- ID
- GENRE2

i Choose File Format to download selected variables:

- Text
- R Data
- S plus
- Stata

[Create Zip File](#)

i Select variables from table below (selected variables will be displayed above)

Show 10 Variables ▾

Variable Information Table

<input type="checkbox"/>	Type	Name	Label	Summary														
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Character	ID	[label missing]															
<input type="checkbox"/>	Character	Name	[label missing]															
<input type="checkbox"/>	Character	GENRE1	[label missing]															
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Character	GENRE2	[label missing]	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Value (Label)</th> <th>Frequency</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A'cappella</td> <td>114448.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Acousmatic</td> <td>335.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Acoustic</td> <td>48655.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Afro-beat</td> <td>113417.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Alternative</td> <td>61805.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ambient</td> <td>11024.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Value (Label)	Frequency	A'cappella	114448.0	Acousmatic	335.0	Acoustic	48655.0	Afro-beat	113417.0	Alternative	61805.0	Ambient	11024.0
Value (Label)	Frequency																	
A'cappella	114448.0																	
Acousmatic	335.0																	
Acoustic	48655.0																	
Afro-beat	113417.0																	
Alternative	61805.0																	
Ambient	11024.0																	

Choose a Statistical Model ▼

Choose a Statistical Model ▲

Categorical Data Analysis
 Cross-Tabulation

Ecological Inference Models
 Hierarchical Multinomial-Dirichlet Ecological Inference Model for R x C Tables

Event Count Models
 Negative Binomial Reg for Event Count Dep Vars
 Poisson Reg for Event Count Dep Vars

Models for Continous Bounded Dependent Variables
 Exponential Reg for Duration Dep Vars
 Gamma Reg for Cont, Positive Dep Vars
 Log-Normal Reg for Duration Dep Vars
 Weibull Reg for Duration Dep Vars

Models for Continuous Dependent Variables
 Least Squares Reg for Cont Dep Vars
 Linear regression for Left-Censored Dep Variable

Models for Dichotomous Dependent Variables
 Logistic Reg for Binary Dep Vars
 Probit Reg for Binary Dep Vars
 Rare Events Logistic Reg for Binary Dep Vars

Run Model

s from table below (selected variables will be displayed above)

Show 10 Va

Type	Name	Label	Variable In
Character	ID	[label missing]	Summar
Character	Name	[label missing]	
Character	GENRE1	[label missing]	
Character	GENRE2	[label missing]	

Dataverse After

Scholars Portal **Dataverse**

Q Search

[About](#)

[Guides](#) ▾

[Support](#)

[Dashboard](#)

 [Kevin Worthington](#) ▾

Fr (Beta)

[University of Ottawa Dataverse](#)

[Scholars Portal Dataverse](#) > **University of Ottawa Dataverse**

 [Edit](#) ▾

Q Find

[Advanced Search](#)

+ [Add Data](#) ▾

 Dataverses (9)

 Datasets (13)

 Files (61)

Publication Status

[Published \(14\)](#)

[Unpublished \(5\)](#)

[Draft \(3\)](#)

[Deaccessioned \(1\)](#)

Publication Date

[2014 \(8\)](#)

1 to 10 of 22 Results

 [Sort](#) ▾

Dramatic Growth of Open Access

Jun 29, 2016 - Dramatic Growth of Open Access Dataverse

Morrison, Heather, 2014, "Dramatic Growth of Open Access", hdl:10864/10660, Scholars Portal Dataverse, V13

Macro level data depicting the growth of open access. Updated quarterly (March 31, June 30, September 30, December 31 and usually an early December early year-end edition). This is a spreadsheet with multiple tab. The intention is to regularly update this dataverse with the latest...

Dramatic Growth of Open Access **Draft**

Jun 29, 2016 - Dramatic Growth of Open Access Dataverse

Morrison, Heather, 2014, "Dramatic Growth of Open Access", hdl:10864/10660, Scholars Portal Dataverse, DRAFT VERSION

Search this dataset...

Q Find

21 Files

Download

<input type="checkbox"/>	D_BLB_ORIG_FTR_FridgeTemp and D_BLB_ORIG_FTR_Survival Documentation	
<input type="checkbox"/>	A_BLB_ORIG_Lipids2013_Metadata.txt Plain Text - 384 bytes - Oct 24, 2016 - 0 Downloads MD5: 79570d408fd0757c3bc7be027b2345fe; An explanation of the abbreviations and codes used in the ORIGINAL data file 'D_BLB_ORIG_Lipids2013'. Documentation	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	A_BLB_ORIG_SurvivalEmerg_Metadata.txt Plain Text - 719 bytes - Oct 24, 2016 - 0 Downloads MD5: 06a70a4b5e171417a67be16044447f5e; An explanation of the abbreviations and codes used in the ORIGINAL data file 'D_BLB_ORIG_SurvivalEmerg'. Documentation	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	A_BLB_ORIG_Temp_Metadata.txt Plain Text - 662 bytes - Oct 24, 2016 - 0 Downloads MD5: d91362d102f708d55abb705a6f62eb97; An explanation of the abbreviations and codes used in the ORIGINAL data files 'D_BLB_ORIG_Temp2011', 'D_BLB_ORIG_Temp2012' and 'D_BLB_ORIG_Temp2013'. Documentation	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	A_BLB_PROCD_Codebook.pdf Adobe PDF - 126.3 KB - Oct 24, 2016 - 2 Downloads MD5: 14b173fe8040c808142b18290abb7470; Explanation of the variables and codes found in the processed data files. Documentation	Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	D_BLB_ORIG_FTR_FridgeTemp.tab Tabular Data - 1.4 MB - Oct 24, 2016 - 0 Downloads 34 Variables, 6526 Observations - UNF:6:VH8VPEmpTdpW7LbjpmWdQ== See the file 'A_BLB_ORIG_FTR_Metadata' for an explanation of abbreviations and codes found in this file. Original data	Explore Download
<input type="checkbox"/>	D_BLB_ORIG_FTR_Survival.tab Tabular Data - 1.4 KB - Oct 24, 2016 - 0 Downloads 8 Variables, 54 Observations - UNF:6:1HBu9isLprkJQcLpCLoHQ== See the file 'A_BLB_ORIG_FTR_Metadata' for an explanation of abbreviations and codes found in this file. Original data	Explore Download

TwoRavens Advanced Analysis Tool

Base_Hpp

exp(codmun)

Estimate

Data Selection

Variables Subset

- COD
- codmun
- municipio
- uf
- sorteio
- data_sort
- year_sort
- ind_corrup_n
- total_os
- ind_corrup_m
- tot_montante
- htransfers
- personnel
- medsupplies
- investment
- providers

History

Model Selection

Models Set Covar. Results

- ls
- logit
- probit
- poisson
- normal
- gamma
- negbinom
- exp
- lognorm
- tobit
- quantile
- logitgee
- probitgee
- zgammagee
- znormalgee
- doissonodee

Custom Development List

- Internationalization
- Custom splash page
- Institutional
 - Dataverse mapping
 - Affiliation using IP Groups
 - Redirecting
- Data Explorer

Data Explorer

DDI Explorer - Beta

Français

Survey of Secondary School Students, 2004 [Canada]

The Canada Millennium Scholarship Foundation, 2015, "Survey of Secondary School Students"

Q x **123** Results [Download My Variables](#) [Chart My Variables](#) [Download All](#) ▾

[Advanced Analysis](#) ↗

My Variables Select All Clear	ID	Name	Label	Categories	Valid Cases
<input type="checkbox"/>	116753	id	Identification number		
<input type="checkbox"/>	116748	province	Province	5	
<input type="checkbox"/>	116814	school	School		
<input type="checkbox"/>	116836	a1	What grade are you in	9	
<input type="checkbox"/>	116803	a2	In what country were you born	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	116815	a3	Are you male or female	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	116797	a4	Have a intellectual/physical/learning disability	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	116784	a5	Are you an Aboriginal person	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	116730	a6	Are you a member of a visible minority group	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	116728	a7i	Language speak at home most often:English		

First « **1** 2 3 4 5 » Last

Records Per Page 10 ▾

Values	Categories	N
1	Male	7070
2	Female	7181
9	No response	78

Summary Statistics

Cases

N

Close

Variable: Barriers for educ past hs:paying for living expenses

Values	Categories	N
1	A major barrier	754
2	A significant barrier	1302
3	Somewhat of a barrier	2189
4	A relatively minor barrier	1750
5	No barrier at all	1450
9	No response	155

Summary Statistics

Close

Survey of Seco
The Canada Millennium

Q x

My Variables
Select All Clear

ID
116772
116798
116760
116773
116749
116835
116740
116822
116777
116738

First « 3 4 5 6 7

The Results

- Launched Dataverse 4.6 with Data Explorer in October 2016
- Presented during the weekly Dataverse community call
- Received interest from several institutions
- Conferenced-called with Dataverse developers who expressed interest in rolling it into a future release

Technology Used

- Code ported from ODESI.ca
 - Our In-house DDI Explorer
- JavaScript libraries
 - AngularJS v1.3.9, Bootstrap v3.0.2, jQuery v1.11.2, jQuery UI - v1.12.1 (Recently added)
 - Google Chart API Directive Module for AngularJS version 0.0.9

Available on git

<https://github.com/scholarsportal/Dataverse-Data-Explorer>

Dataverse Tab File Explore

- Supported File Formats
 - SPSS (POR and SAV formats) ver. 7-22
 - STATA ver. 4-13
 - R ver. -3
 - Excel XLSX
 - CSV (limited support)
- Enable TwoRavensTabularView
- Requires Rserve installation
- Hijack the Explore button
 - Javascript, JSF, Java

Dataverse DDI

- Use API to load DDI codebook ver. 2
 - `{host}/api/access/datafile/{internal id}/metadata/ddi`
 - Missing frequencies
- Load Prep file
 - `{host}/api/access/datafile/{internal id}?format=prep`

Next Steps

- Enhance Dataverse DDI support
 - Working group established
- Establish long-term Data Explorer integration
 - Currently merging in with each upgrade
 - Talks of using Java Service Provider Interface (SPI) and establishing an app registry
- Enhance Data Explorer

Enhance Data Explorer

test

Admin, Dataverse, 2016

✕
22 Results
Download My Variables
Download All

Table View [Chart View](#)

ID	Name	Label
123	Q1	1. Overall, do you approve or disapprove of the job John Tory is doing as mayor?
118	Q2	2. Overall, do you approve or disapprove of the job Rob Ford is doing as a city councilor?
126	Q3	3. Who is a better mayor, John Tory or Rob Ford?
120	Q4	4. Would you approve or disapprove of a sales tax in Toronto?
111	Q5	5. Would you approve or disapprove of a sales tax in Toronto if it balanced the budget and paid for needed infrastructure?
112	Q6	6. Do you approve or disapprove of Mayor Tory's SmartTrack rail transit plan?
122	Q7	7. Will the SmartTrack rail transit plan benefit you personally or not?
109	Q8	8. Have you driven on St Clair Avenue West in the past year or not?
115	Q9	9. How well does traffic flow on St Clair Avenue West?
107	Q10	10. Do you agree or disagree St Clair Avenue West is a traffic disaster?

First « **1** 2 3 » Last

Records Per Page 10

+4. Would you approve or disapprove of a sales tax in Toronto?	+5. Would you approve or disapprove of a sales tax in Toronto if it balanced the budget and paid for needed infrastructure?	+7. Will the SmartTrack rail transit plan benefit you personally or not?	%
Approve	Approve	Yes	5.3
		No	12.4
		Don't know	3.2
	Disapprove	Yes	0.2
		No	0.7
		Don't know	0.1
Disapprove	Approve	Yes	0.5
		No	0.1
		Don't know	0.1
	Disapprove	Yes	4.1
		No	8.8
		Don't know	2
Don't know	Yes	8	
	No	30.2	
	Don't know	6.4	
Don't know	Yes	0.7	
	No	3.1	
Don't know	Don't know	1	

Feature Enhancements (wish list)

- Custom tabulations and charting
- cross tabulations
- Filtering cases / variables
- Weighting
- Recoding
- Combining datasets from across dataverses (different sources)
- Integration of visualization with discovery of variables
- Variable grouping

Recap

- Dataverse supports many files which can be explored
- Current offering lacks intuitiveness
- APIs allow metadata to be accessed
- Plugging-in a existing explorer made possible with shared DDI standard
- More work to be done

Kevin Worthington, MASC

Applications Programmer/Analyst - Data & GIS Services

OCUL Scholars Portal

kevin.worthington@utoronto.ca

